

Intensification of the reverse water–gas shift process using a countercurrent chemical looping regenerative reactor

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ABSTRACT

Chemical reactions have thermodynamic limits on species conversion which can negatively impact process design. Unconverted feedstock often needs to be separated and recycled, increasing energy demand, process complexity and cost. Just as is the case for heat exchangers, countercurrent reactor systems can improve the thermodynamic limits on species exchange and conversion. This work describes and demonstrates a countercurrent redox reactor system, which can be realised in a packed-bed chemical-looping reactor by storing the favourable oxygen chemical potential inclines using the unique properties of non-stoichiometric oxides. The concept is analogous to a regenerative heat exchanger, but for oxygen exchange and storage, and so we use the term *regenerative reactor*. We apply this approach to the reverse water–gas shift reaction, which is a critical step in the processing of synthetic e-fuels. The concept is modelled and experimentally validated via a lab-scale demonstration performed with CeO₂ at 1073 K, which resulted in a CO₂-to-CO molar conversion of 88 %, compared to a thermodynamic limit of 58 % for the conventional process at the same conditions. The modelling results indicate that the ideal thermodynamic conversion can be approximately doubled via this method. Furthermore, the CO is formed separately from the H₂ flow, allowing for the syngas composition to be finely tuned for downstream processing.

1. Introduction

The reverse water gas shift (RWGS) reaction given by

is a key process for CO₂ conversion and utilisation [1,2]. Particularly in *Power-to-X* process chains [3], where H₂ produced via water electrolysis can be reacted with CO₂ to form syngas, a mixture of CO and H₂ suitable for the synthesis of hydrocarbon based fuels and chemicals.

The RWGS reaction is endothermic, with a small increase in entropy, making it more favourable at high temperatures, where the standard Gibbs free energy change becomes negative above 1096 K (ESI Figure 1). The reaction has equal moles of gases in the reactants and products, making its equilibrium composition independent of pressure. The thermodynamics of the reaction are therefore quite restrictive, requiring high temperatures and significant excess H₂ to achieve appreciable CO₂ conversion (see Fig. 2c). This has a detrimental effect on the practical implementation of the process and the quality of the syngas that can be produced. High temperature operation increases the energy demand and reactor design complexity. On the other hand, supplying hydrogen in excess of 3H₂ : 1CO₂ results in a syngas composition that is not optimal for most gas-to-liquid technologies, requiring additional

separation steps that will further penalise the efficiency and cost of the process.

The equilibrium of the RWGS reaction can be shifted to greater CO₂ conversion by *in-situ* removal of the product H₂O [4], using sorbents [5,6], or H₂O permeable membranes [7,8]. However, these concepts add significant complexity and design constraints to the process, with sorbents having temperature limitations and requiring cyclic regeneration, while membrane reactors require large surface areas and sweep gas to remove the H₂O. Neither concept has progressed beyond the lab scale.

The thermodynamic limits on CO₂ conversion could be significantly increased if the RWGS reaction were performed across an oxygen permeable membrane reactor with a countercurrent flow configuration (see Fig. 2d) [9]. Such a countercurrent reactor could be realised using mixed electronic ionic conducting oxides as the membrane [10,11]. However, such membrane reactors are difficult to fabricate, the production rates are limited by the membrane area and transport properties, and their scalability is unproven. In this work we propose an alternative process configuration that takes advantage of the favourable countercurrent flow thermodynamics, namely; a two-step chemical looping cycle of a non-stoichiometric metal oxide in a packed-bed reactor with alternating flow directions of the H₂ and CO₂. The RWGS reaction then

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Fig. 1. A schematic of the reverse water-gas shift reaction performed in a countercurrent chemical-looping regenerative reactor. The packed-bed of non-stoichiometric oxide stores an incline of oxygen chemical potential between the reduction and oxidation steps, that can be used to achieve greater conversion of CO_2 in the reverse flow.

takes place via two separate redox reaction steps, with oxygen being periodically exchanged and stored in a metal oxide MO_x .

The non-stoichiometry δ indicates the reduction extent of the metal oxide. Metal oxides which undergo non-stoichiometric reduction include $\text{CeO}_{2-\delta}$ [12], and many perovskites [13]. These oxides can accommodate oxygen vacancies in their crystal lattice, which are free to move through the lattice, exhibiting solution-like behaviour in the solid [14], resulting in a continuous spectrum of oxygen non-stoichiometry under changing temperature and oxygen partial pressure [12]. The oxygen chemical potential μ_O then depends on δ . The proposed concept takes advantage of this property to realise the thermodynamic benefits of countercurrent operation as illustrated in Fig. 1.

This process configuration avoids the design complexity and constraints of a membrane reactor, utilising instead the *workhorse* of the chemical process industry, a packed-bed reactor, with a better outlook for scale-up. In fact, the steam iron process utilised redox chemical looping of iron oxide for hydrogen production, and was applied on an industrial scale for several decades in the first half of the 20th century [15].

A good analogy for the process is that of a fixed matrix regenerative heat exchanger (or thermozone heat storage), where sensible heat from a high temperature fluid is temporarily stored in a solid medium with a temperature distribution (thermozone) along the solid [16]. The heat is then recovered by reversing the flow and transferring the stored heat. Such a regenerator can approach the performance of an ideal countercurrent heat exchanger. The concept here is analogous, but oxygen is stored instead of heat, with an incline of μ_O instead of temperature.

Performing the RWGS reaction in a chemical looping process is already an active area of research [17,18]. An intrinsic benefit of this processes vis-a-vis conventional co-feeding is the flexibility to tune the syngas composition due to the inherent separation of the product streams of the two redox steps (Eqs. (2) and (3)), limiting the need for further separation processes before gas-to-liquid conversion [19]. However, the CO_2 conversion benefit demonstrated here comes from combining the unique properties of non-stoichiometric oxides with countercurrent operation.

This countercurrent chemical-looping reactor concept has also been proposed and experimentally demonstrated for hydrogen production via the water-gas shift process [20]. Metcalfe et al. measured a steam conversion extent of 95% relative to a thermodynamic limit of 50% for the conventional catalytic process at the same conditions. This extraordinary result led the authors to suggest the process may no longer be constrained by equilibrium thermodynamics or irreversible effects. They provided a more robust physical model in a follow up study [21]. Indeed, the process concept is still limited by thermodynamic equilibrium constraints, which in this case depend on the μ_O profiles

of the countercurrent flows, and the available oxygen storage chemical potential profile of the non-stoichiometric oxide, $\mu_O(\delta)$.

In this work, we model and demonstrate the chemical looping regenerative reactor concept applied to the RWGS process. We first illustrate the potential improvement in thermodynamic limits for the RWGS reaction by considering an idealised countercurrent membrane reactor. We then formulate a 1-D time dependent model of a countercurrent chemical looping reactor based on CeO_2 . Finally, packed-bed reactor experiments are performed to test and validate the potential improvement in CO_2 conversion. The model implementations, experimental data, and data analysis have been made publicly available.¹

2. Countercurrent RWGS

To illustrate the benefits of countercurrent oxygen exchange in the reverse water-gas shift reaction we can compare an idealised countercurrent membrane reactor to a conventional co-feeding catalytic process as illustrated in Fig. 2. Note that a cocurrent membrane reactor has the same thermodynamic limits as a cofeeding catalytic reactor [9]. The thermodynamic limits of the conventional case shown in Fig. 2c were calculated using the open-source thermochemistry library *cantera* [22]. The default gri-mech 3.0 database was modified by removing hydrocarbons such as CH_4 , to avoid side reactions in the equilibrium calculations.

The countercurrent membrane case comprises two separate reaction steps which sum up to the RWGS reaction,

The oxygen produced by the CO_2 reduction reaction (Eq. (4)) is transferred across the membrane to oxidise H_2 (Eq. (5)). In order to satisfy the conditions of thermodynamic spontaneity, the oxygen must move downhill in chemical potential. In other words, the chemical potential of oxygen in the CO_2 flow, $\mu_{\text{O},\text{CO}_2}$, must be greater than or equal to that in the H_2 flow, $\mu_{\text{O},\text{H}_2}$,

$$\mu_{\text{O},\text{CO}_2}(x) \geq \mu_{\text{O},\text{H}_2}(x) \quad (6)$$

at all points x along a countercurrent reactor. This is illustrated in Fig. 2b and e. This condition is used to calculate the thermodynamic limits according to a methodology developed in previous work [9]. Note that the co-feeding case has the same thermodynamic limits as a cocurrent membrane reactor.

The main takeaway from the results is that the chemical potential profiles in the countercurrent case allow for a significant increase in oxygen transfer relative to the conventional case. Comparing Fig. 2c

¹ https://github.com/bulfin/RWGS_chemical_looping_regenerative_reactors.

Fig. 2. Thermodynamic limits of co-feeding RWGS compared to a countercurrent oxygen permeable membrane process. **a.** A conventional co-feed packed-bed catalytic reactor. **b.** Oxygen chemical potential plotted vs. reaction extent to illustrate the spontaneous transfer of oxygen from higher to lower chemical potential until equilibrium is reached. **c.** Equilibrium CO_2 conversion for the co-feed reactor vs. temperature and excess hydrogen. **d.** A countercurrent membrane reactor. **e.** Oxygen chemical potential as a function of reaction extent in the countercurrent configuration, showing the potential for complete conversion. **f.** Equilibrium CO_2 conversion for the countercurrent reactor vs. temperature and excess hydrogen.

and **f**, the CO_2 conversion could be approximately doubled, while being capped at 1, which is complete conversion. Taking an excess H_2 flow of $2\text{H}_2 : 1\text{CO}_2$ as an example, the countercurrent case could achieve 97% CO_2 conversion at 873 K, compared to just 52% for the conventional co-feed process.

3. Chemical looping regenerative reactor model

The countercurrent chemical looping regenerator reactor concept should offer a similar improvement in thermodynamic limits as a countercurrent membrane reactor. Provided the non-stoichiometric oxide has a range of oxygen chemical potentials $\mu_{\text{O}}(\delta)$, which covers the shaded region in **Fig. 2(e)**, it should be possible to use alternating countercurrent flows to effectively store and then utilise the favourable μ_{O} profiles. To illustrate this concept, a 1-D transient model was formulated for an isothermal isobaric packed-bed reactor. The non-stoichiometric oxide $\text{CeO}_{2-\delta}$ was selected for the model, and the subsequent experimental demonstration, due to its well characterised thermodynamic properties [12,23], and its proven chemical stability over multiple consecutive redox cycles [24].

The model consists of the convection–diffusion equation for the gas phase, coupled via a source term to a local ordinary differential equation (ODE) of δ in $\text{CeO}_{2-\delta}$. The δ -ODE is an idealised kinetic term which rapidly brings the gas and solid towards equilibrium (see **Fig. 3a** and **d**). In this way, the transient model approaches equilibrium between the solid and gas phases, and serves to highlight the thermodynamic limits of the process. While the goal was to illustrate the thermodynamic limits of the process, diffusion (an irreversible process) was also included as it helps to stabilise the numerical model. Below we offer a brief description of the model, with full details, including all operating parameters, boundary conditions and results given in section 2 of the ESI.

For the reduction step (Eq. (2)), the mass transfer in the gas phase was modelled using the convection–diffusion equation for steam H_2O in the H_2 flow,

$$\epsilon_{\text{bed}} \frac{\partial C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial(u_s C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}})}{\partial x} + D_{\text{eff}} \frac{\partial^2 C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{\partial x^2} + C_{\text{CeO}_2} \left(\frac{\partial \delta}{\partial t} \right) \quad (7)$$

where ϵ_{bed} is the void fraction of the packed bed, $C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is the local steam concentration, u_s is the superficial velocity of the gas in the bed, D_{eff} is the effective diffusion coefficient of the H_2O in H_2 , and C_{CeO_2} is the concentration of the oxide CeO_2 in the packed bed. The solution also gives the hydrogen concentration since the gas only has two components and $p = p_{\text{H}_2} + p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, and using the ideal gas law $C_i = \frac{p_i}{RT}$.

The source term is an ordinary differential equation of the local non-stoichiometry δ given by,

$$\frac{d\delta}{dt} = k_0(\delta_{\text{eq}} - \delta)\theta(\delta_{\text{eq}} - \delta) \quad (8)$$

where k_0 is the rate constant (units $[\text{s}^{-1}]$), δ is the local non-stoichiometry, δ_{eq} is the local equilibrium non-stoichiometry with the local gas phase composition, (i.e. $\delta_{\text{eq}}(C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}})$), and θ is a Heaviside step function, which terminates the reaction if it exceeds equilibrium. Our model then consists of two independent variables $C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}(x, t)$ and $\delta(x, t)$, with a partial differential equation of $C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ coupled to a local ordinary differential equation of δ .

The local equilibrium non-stoichiometry δ_{eq} is calculated using the equilibrium oxygen partial pressure for the gas phase, which is that of the water splitting reaction $\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}_2 + 0.5\text{O}_2$ and is given by,

$$p_{\text{O}_2} = p^\circ \left(K_{\text{ws}} \left(\frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{1 - x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} \right) \right)^2 \quad (9)$$

where p° is the reference pressure of 1 bar, K_{ws} is the equilibrium constant of the water splitting reaction, and $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is the steam mole

Fig. 3. A 1-D transient model of a $\text{CeO}_{2-\delta}$ packed-bed reactor undergoing first reduction under H_2 and then re-oxidation under CO_2 with the opposite flow direction. **a.** A schematic of the reduction step, and the equilibrium mole fraction of H_2O vs. δ in $\text{CeO}_{2-\delta}$. **b.** Reduction extent δ vs. the position in the reactor plotted at various times during the reduction up until the stop condition, $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O},\text{out}} = 0.5$. **c.** The outlet H_2O mole fraction vs. time, which is the instantaneous H_2 conversion extent. **d.** A schematic of the oxidation step, with the equilibrium mole fraction of CO_2 vs. δ in $\text{CeO}_{2-\delta}$. **e.** Reduction extent δ vs. the position plotted at various times during the oxidation up until the stop condition, $x_{\text{CO}_2,\text{out}} = 0.5$. **f.** The outlet CO mole fraction vs. time, which is the instantaneous CO_2 conversion extent.

fraction. This oxygen partial pressure and the temperature can be used to calculate the equilibrium non-stoichiometry using equilibrium data for CeO_2 . Here we use a simple analytical model of non-stoichiometry which has good agreement with experiments over the ranges of non-stoichiometry and temperature considered here [25]. The equilibrium non-stoichiometry as a function of $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ at 1073 K is shown in Fig. 3a.

The model was implemented using the finite element method software COMSOL Multiphysics. The oxygen mass balance and adherence to equilibrium limits were used to ensure the physical consistency of the model. The rate constant k_0 and the time stepping were adjusted to ensure that the solution was stable, and that the reaction closely followed equilibrium.

Eq. (7) was also used to model the reversed CO_2 flow, with C_{CO_2} substituted for $C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$. The direction of the superficial velocity was switched $u_s \rightarrow -u_s$, and the sign of the source term was adjusted via the ODE so that CO_2 is consumed by the reaction,

$$\frac{d\delta}{dt} = -k_0(\delta - \delta_{\text{eq}})\theta(\delta - \delta_{\text{eq}}). \quad (10)$$

The thermodynamic equilibrium δ_{eq} was calculated in the same way, but using the CO_2 splitting thermodynamics, $\text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO} + 0.5\text{O}_2$.

Finally, the reader should note that the purpose of the model is not to accurately simulate the behaviour of a specific reactor and operating parameters. Rather it is meant to highlight the improved thermodynamic limits of CO_2 conversion for the process, relative to the conventional co-feed case.

The main parameters of the model are given in Table 1. The operating temperature was selected based on the thermodynamic properties of $\text{CeO}_{2-\delta}$, which due to its strong oxygen bond requires relatively high temperature to undergo appreciable reduction under H_2 . The CeO_2 concentration ($C_{\text{CeO}_2} = 10\,000 \text{ [mol m}^{-3}\text{]}$) and the packed bed void fraction (ϵ_{bed}) correspond to a loosely packed bed of 40% dense granules. The governing equations were discretised and solved using a finite element method with direct time stepping. The physical consistency was verified

Table 1

Main operating parameters of the packed-bed reactor model.

Parameter	Value	Unit
Temperature	1073	[K]
Pressure	1	[bar]
Length	1	[m]
Concentration of CeO_2	C_{CeO_2}	$10\,000 \text{ [mol m}^{-3}\text{]}$
Packed bed void fraction	ϵ	0.4 [-]
Superficial gas velocity	u_s	0.05 or $-0.05 \text{ [m s}^{-1}\text{]}$

using the oxygen mass balance and the adherence to equilibrium limits at all times throughout the reactor domain.

The model results are shown in Fig. 3 for the second simulated cycle (after one reduction and one oxidation, starting with the second reduction), where the first cycle started with fully oxidised ceria, CeO_2 , which would not represent a closed cycle. The complete results for the two consecutive cycles are given in section 2 of the ESI, including the oxygen mass balance and plots showing the adherence to equilibrium limits. It can be seen that during the reduction step (Fig. 3b and c) δ increases with time and exhibits a spatial profile that peaks at the inlet and monotonically decreases towards the outlet. The reduction step was stopped when the H_2O mole fraction at the outlet reached 50%. At this point there is a pronounced incline in the extent of reduction δ across the bed, which also corresponds to a $\mu_{\text{O}}(x)$ incline. The total amount of stored oxygen is proportional to the grey shaded region between the initial and final oxidation states. During the oxidation step (Fig. 3e and f) the flow is reversed and the packed bed is re-oxidised with CO_2 , with δ decreasing as the oxygen vacancies are filled. As the CO_2 moves through the reactor, from right to left, the larger δ and lower μ_{O} makes it increasingly favourable for CO formation. The oxidation step was stopped when the CO mole fraction at the outlet reached 50%. Integrating the flows over the entire cycle gives a CO_2 cumulative molar conversion of 96%, with an excess H_2 of $\text{H}_2/\text{CO}_2 = 1.11$. The thermodynamic limit for the conventional co-feeding process at these conditions with the same feed ratio is 52%. The model indicates the

Fig. 4. Experimental demonstration of the countercurrent chemical looping process concept. **a.** A schematic of the experimental setup showing the main components and flow paths. **b.** The cumulative molar conversion of CO_2 and H_2 over a complete cycle for the chemical looping cases compared to the co-feeding experiment. Also shown are peak CO_2 conversions, and the thermodynamic limit (TL) of the co-fed case. **c.** The time evolution of the measured temperature, input flow rates, and mole fractions of species in the outflow during countercurrent, cocurrent and co-feeding experiments.

significantly improved conversion of CO_2 with inherent separation of the product CO.

4. Experimental demonstration

To experimentally demonstrate the process, a tubular packed-bed reactor setup was assembled as illustrated in Fig. 4a. The switching of the flow direction was achieved using a combination of four 3-way valves and alternative flow paths around the reactor. The following parameters were measured: the temperature at the centre of the bed, pressure before the bed, inlet mass flow rates, and concentrations of CO , CO_2 , and H_2 in the outflow.

The input mass flow rates were calibrated using a flow definer and were accurate within 1% of the set-point. The gas analysis systems used were a Siemens Ultramat and Siemens Calomat. The Ultramat uses an Infra-red sensor configured to measure CO , CO_2 , and CH_4 concentration, as well as an electrochemical sensor for O_2 concentration. The Calomat system can detect hydrogen using a thermal conductivity sensor (k -sensor). The CH_4 and O_2 signals remained at zero throughout the experiments. The H_2O is condensed out of the flow, hence its part of the mass balance must be inferred from the H_2 signal.

The packed bed was formed of CeO_2 granules manufactured from CeO_2 powder (Sigma Aldrich 211575) according to a liquid drop method [26], which included a final annealing step at 1873 K for

8 h to ensure sintering. The resulting granules were approximately spherical in shape with diameters of 1.37 ± 0.14 mm, and a density of 1.44 ± 0.14 g cm^{-3} . The large resulting void fraction of 80% [27] was visually confirmed by SEM imaging of cleaved granules (ESI Fig. 3).

Using preliminary thermogravimetric analysis of the granules (ESI Figure 4) and considering the idealised model results shown in Fig. 3, 1073 K was selected as the operating temperature. The reactor was operated at atmospheric pressure. The input flow rates were set at 0.3 slm (standard litres per minute), which was the minimum flow required by the gas analysis instrumentation. The resulting residence time in the packed bed was in the range of 1–2 s. The gaseous feedstock H_2 and CO_2 were supplied using 5% mixtures in Ar. This allowed for sufficient cycle time to obtain good gas analysis resolution, without affecting the thermodynamic limits of the process, which are pressure independent. The packed bed parameters are given in Table 2.

Three types of experiment were performed in the system: (1) countercurrent chemical looping with alternating flow directions of H_2 and CO_2 , (2) cocurrent chemical looping with alternating flows of H_2 and CO_2 in the same direction, and (3) conventional co-feeding of H_2 and CO_2 , where the ceria packed bed acts as a catalyst. The molar ratio of the H_2 and CO_2 flows in the co-feeding experiment was set to match the ratio of reactants fed over the complete countercurrent cycle, $1.5H_2:1CO_2$. The main experimental results for the three cases are shown in Fig. 4, where one countercurrent cycle was performed before

Table 2
Parameters of the packed-bed reactor experimental setup.

Length	L	30.2	[cm]
Diameter	d	1.83	[cm]
Mass loading	m_{CeO_2}	83.2	[g]
Oxide concentration	C_{CeO_2}	6087	[mol m ⁻³]
Temperature set-point	T_{set}	1073	[K]
Average bed temperature	T	1063	[K]
Operating pressure	p	1.03	[bar]
Granule void fraction	$\epsilon_{\text{granule}}$	0.8 ± 0.1	[-]
Bed void fraction	ϵ_{bed}	0.27 ± 0.04	[-]

the results shown so as not to start with a completely oxidised bed, which would affect the oxygen mass balance over a complete cycle. Complete datasets for the experiments are available in the ESI.

For comparison, Fig. 4c shows an experimental run with countercurrent, cocurrent and co-feed experiments performed consecutively under the same operating conditions. Between the oxidation and reduction steps of the chemical looping cycles, pure argon was flowed through the reactor for 3 min, to clear the reactor and allow for an accurate mass balance of each step. For the reduction step, the H₂ flow was stopped when its concentration reached 3.4%. For the oxidation step, the CO₂ flow was stopped when the CO concentration dropped to 90% of its peak value. There was approximately a 1-min delay for the gas leaving the reactor to reach the gas analysis system, resulting in a delay in the response after the stop conditions were reached. For the oxidation step, the CO concentration can be seen to drop rapidly, which is in agreement with the modelling results.

The total number of moles of H₂ or CO₂ fed to the reactor over a single chemical looping cycle were calculated as the integral of the inflow,

$$n_{i,0} = \frac{1}{V_m} \int_{t_{\text{start}}}^{t_{\text{end}}} x_{i,0} v_0 dt. \quad (11)$$

where t_{start} and t_{end} are the start and finishing times of the cycle, V_m is the molar volume, $x_{i,0}$ is the mole fraction of H₂ or CO₂ in the feed (0.05) and v_0 is the standard volumetric flow rate into the system.

The total number of moles of CO, H₂ or CO₂ flowing out of the reactor were calculated according to the measured mole fractions at the outflow $x_{i,\text{gas analysis}}$,

$$n_{i,f} = \frac{1}{V_m} \int_{t_{\text{start}}}^{t_{\text{end}}} x_{i,\text{gas analysis}} v_f dt. \quad (12)$$

These integrals include the time after the flow is switched to argon in order to include the trail off of all species and obtain a complete mass balance. For CO and CO₂ mass balances during the oxidation step the standard volumetric flow out is equal to the flow in $v_f = v_0$. In the case of the H₂ mass balance during reduction we need to account for the fact that the steam is condensed out of the flow which changes the out-flow rate,

$$v_f = \frac{v_0(1 - x_{\text{H}_2,0})}{1 - x_{\text{H}_2,\text{gas-analysis}}}. \quad (13)$$

The total moles of steam leaving the system must be calculated from the change in moles of hydrogen $n_{\text{H}_2,0,f} = n_{\text{H}_2,0} - n_{\text{H}_2,f}$.

The conversion extents of CO₂ and H₂ over the whole cycle are then defined as,

$$X_i = 1 - \frac{n_{i,f}}{n_{i,0}}. \quad (14)$$

The closed mass balance of carbon and oxygen were tested according to the equalities $n_{\text{CO}_2,0} = n_{\text{CO}_2,f} + n_{\text{CO},f}$ and $n_{\text{CO},f} = n_{\text{H}_2,0,f}$ respectively, which held within the error of the measurements.

For the co-feed experiments, we have a continuous process, and so the average mole fractions over a period of 15 min were used to calculate the CO₂ conversion extent

$$X_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{\bar{x}_{\text{CO}}}{\bar{x}_{\text{CO}} + \bar{x}_{\text{CO}_2}}. \quad (15)$$

Fig. 5. The number of moles of CO and H₂O produced per cycle plotted for 10 consecutive countercurrent cycles. The net conversion of CO₂ per cycle is also plotted on the right hand axes.

In the co-feed results the raw CALOMAT hydrogen signal was corrected for cross sensitivity to CO and CO₂. The volumetric outflow v_f was also corrected according to Eq. (13) to account for condensed steam. The conversion extent of H₂ was then calculated according to the average molar inflow and outflow of H₂ over a 15 min period,

$$X_{\text{H}_2} = 1 - \frac{\bar{F}_{\text{H}_2,f}}{\bar{F}_{\text{H}_2,0}}. \quad (16)$$

where $F_{\text{H}_2,f}$ is the molar outflow of H₂ and $F_{\text{H}_2,0}$ is the molar inflow H₂.

Fig. 4b shows the calculated CO₂ and H₂ molar conversions (X_i) obtained for the experiments shown in Fig. 4c. The countercurrent case offered the greatest conversion, validating the process concept and the improved thermodynamic limits predicted by the reactor model shown in Fig. 3. This result is quite remarkable given that the packed bed was only 30 cm long with a free volume residence time of less than 2 s. The stopping conditions could also have been optimised to further improve the net conversion.

The total flow rate in the co-feed case was varied in the range $v = 1.3 - 0.4$ slm, with a fixed feed ratio, to check for kinetic limitations. No effect was seen, indicating the reaction approached thermodynamic equilibrium. This was confirmed by comparison to the calculated thermodynamic limit of X_{CO_2} at the same conditions seen in Fig. 3b. The cocurrent case also outperformed the co-feeding in terms of X_{CO_2} . This can be explained by the fact that the CO₂ flowing through the reactor is exposed to a μ_0 which on average lies between the case of co-feeding and countercurrent operation. The resulting conversion also lies somewhere between the two cases. In the cocurrent case the CO produced at the start of the reactor can also reduce the ceria at later stages in the reactor via the reverse reaction (Eq. (3)). This makes the cocurrent chemical looping case more difficult to analyse.

Ten consecutive countercurrent cycles were performed with the results shown in Fig. 5 in terms of total moles produced and the CO₂ conversion. The first cycle shows more oxygen released from the bed ($n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} > n_{\text{CO}}$), which was due to the bed starting in a fully oxidised state. Afterwards, the performance was stable, showing no change in total moles produced per cycle. Closed oxygen and carbon mass balances were observed over cycles 2–10 within the uncertainty of the measurements (ESI section 4).

The results shown for CeO₂ are intended to illustrate the process concept. For a scaled-up realisation, a non-stoichiometric metal oxide with a lower enthalpy of reduction is preferable, provided the oxygen affinity remains strong enough to drive the oxidation reaction (Eq. (3)).

This will allow for reduction to take place at lower temperatures with a lower heat demand. Examples of suitable candidate materials are mixed ceria zirconia oxides $Ce_{1-x}Zr_xO_2$ [28], and, $LaFeO_3$ and $LaMnO_3$ based perovskites [29]. Indeed promising results have already been reported for $LaFeO_3$ based perovskites for chemical looping RWGS at lower temperatures [30,31].

Discussion

This countercurrent chemical-looping regenerative reactor concept could allow for high conversion of CO_2 , potentially at temperatures as low as 873 K, with the right non-stoichiometric oxide. This could greatly simplify *power-to-X* process chains, and could be realised in a semi-continuous process using two packed-bed reactors. The feasibility for scale-up of this process appears favourable relative to other methods of shifting the equilibrium of the RWGS reaction, which involve membranes or *in-situ* steam absorption. Indeed, the steam iron process, a closely related chemical looping process, has already been applied for hydrogen production on an industrial scale. Furthermore, the existing knowledge from the fields of redox chemical looping and non-stoichiometric metal oxides can be applied.

The further development of this concept would require identifying non-stoichiometric oxides with the right range of μ_O . The oxides should also exhibit high stability over multiple cycles, being robust against unwanted side reactions such as carbonate or carbon formation. From a kinetics perspective the material must also exhibit high production rates at the desired lower temperatures.

The process concept of using a non-stoichiometric oxide to store a μ_O incline is also of broader interest to the field of chemical looping, and it should allow for lower temperature operation and enhanced conversion in processes such as H_2O/CO_2 splitting and CH_4 reforming. The methodology provided in this work can also provide some guidance for investigating other reaction systems.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The model implementations, experimental data, and data analysis have been made publicly available at https://github.com/bulfinb/RWGS_chemical_looping_regenerative_reactors.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2023.141896>. The supplementary information includes; (1) an Ellingham diagram of the reverse water gas shift reaction (2) a more detailed formulation of the 1-D reactor model and its results, (3) SEM and TGA analysis of the CeO_2 granules and (4) Additional plots of the packed reactor experimental results including the temperature profile measured along the bed, complete datasets of the 10 cycle experiment, and mass balance results.

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